

THE CONTENT AND MANIFESTATIONS OF PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER.

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Abstract. *The article describes the pedagogical and psychological problems of training future teachers for work in secondary schools. Manifestations of innovative activity of the future teacher are divided into groups (types) and their tasks and areas of knowledge are analyzed.*

Keywords: *Innovative words, time, space, pedagogical innovation, innovative forms of activity, teacher-innovator, systematization, areas of knowledge, innovative idea.*

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ И ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ.

Аннотация. *Мақолада умумтаълим мактабларида ишлаш учун бўлажак педагогик кадрларлар тайёрлашнинг педагогик ва психологик муаммолари ёритилган. Бўлажак ўқитувчининг инновацион фаолияти курунишлари гуруҳларга (типларга) бўлинган ва уларнинг вазифалари ҳамда билишлар соҳалари таҳлил қилинган.*

Калит сўзлар: *Инновацион сўзлар, вақт, макон, педагогик инноватика, инновацион фаолият кўрунишлари, ўқитувчи-инноватор, тизимлаштириши, билимлар соҳалари, инновацион голя.*

In order to make reasonable proposals for improving the training of pedagogical staff for general secondary schools, it is necessary to have a clear idea of the content of innovative activities of these staff.

Since the scope of our research in the general system of working on the model is limited to the study of the content of innovative activities of the teacher, our main task is to highlight and scientifically substantiate the most important and typical forms of professional pedagogical activity.

Literature (V.A. Slastyonin, L.S. Podymova, E.P. Morozov, P.I. Pidkasiysty, V.S. Lazerov, N.V. Konoplina. N.R. Yusufbekov, etc.) and independent photography the analysis of the map made it possible to compile a list of innovative activity views for the present day (46,36,29,30,58,59,60,61). More than 50 activity views were allocated. In developing a standard list for a more structured delivery of the materials obtained, we classified them into different levels according to certain characteristics.

The stages of performance analysis are determined by the size of its interpretation. An interpretation dimension is the number of classification bases that correspond to the number of dimensions of the object. These dimensions consist of several gradations, respectively.

Individual manifestations of innovative activity can be distinguished by one characteristic: methods of implementation, description of time and space, emotional tension, and so on. However, the most important thing in distinguishing one type of activity from another is the difference in their subject (object).

In general, teacher activities with general secondary school students take many forms. Each of the bucks will have its own special object.

The objects of various forms of innovative activity of the future teacher are students and pedagogical innovation (this is the difference between the activity of a teacher-innovator and the activity of a teacher who traditionally teaches).

However, any activity includes the goal, the engine, the outcome, and the process of the activity itself. Therefore, at the first level, we divided activities into classes on two bases: object of activity and purpose. As a result, five groups were formed, which we called types of activities (Table 1.1).

Table 1

Groups of views of innovative activity of the future teacher and their functions

Types of activities	Activity classes	Location	
		At the moment	Prophecy(10 years)
I. Transfer of innovative experience	1. Analysis of the content of the news and its evaluation 2. Analysis and evaluation of implementation experience 3. Development of a mechanism for the transfer of innovative proposals	1	3
II. Development of pedagogical innovations	4. Critical analysis of practice 5. Work out problem-solving ideas 6. Development of innovative projects 7. Evaluation of innovative projects	3	1
III. Conducting pedagogical tests	8. Goal setting 9. Planning 10. Implementation 11. Analysis and evaluation of results	4	2
IV. Transfer of innovative experience	12. Goal setting 13. Transfer planning 14. Transmission process 15. Analysis and evaluation	2	4

The purpose of the first type - "activities for the transfer of innovative experience" is to include pedagogical innovations in the content of the educational process. The object can be any - new, previously developed (existing) (except for students). The second type of activity - "development of pedagogical innovations" has a different, sufficiently complex object (educational, didactic, management, etc.) and a different purpose (discovery, invention, proposal, improvement of the stages of the educational process).

The basic tasks for classifying an activity into a secondary level are tasks that are given in a specific context. In our case, the conditions that make a clear overall goal a specific task are the time and place of the activity. Thus, at the second level, classification was performed on four bases (object, purpose, place, and time).

Let's look at the first type of activity - 'transferring an innovative experience'. It included three classes of activities that differed in the tasks that general secondary school teachers had to solve.

First class - "Analysis and evaluation of news content"; The task is to analyze and evaluate the level of novelty of pedagogical experience. The second class - "Analysis of the introduction of experience and its evaluation"; The task is to obtain information on the scope of its implementation. Third class - "Development of a mechanism for the transfer of innovative proposals"; The task is to develop a development plan for the acquisition of new movements.

The quality of the second type of activity "development of pedagogical innovations" includes four classes of activities. The first class is 'critical analysis of practice', whose task is to determine the level of elaboration of the problem in pedagogical theory and practice. The second class is "looking for problem-solving ideas," whose task is to identify existing conflicts and choose ways and means to resolve them. "Development of innovative projects" is the third class, whose task is to distinguish the stages of design, to determine the goals of each stage, the timing of their implementation. Finally, the fourth class is the "evaluation of innovative projects," whose task is to evaluate performance.

The third type of activity is 'pedagogical testing', which includes four classes of activities. First class - goal setting; task - to perform the main tasks of the test; the second class - planning - involves the development of a research program, raising the main question. The task of the third class is to obtain new scientific information that proves the hypothesis put forward using the necessary methods based on the research conducted. The task of the fourth grade, called "Analysis and Evaluation of Results," is to draw conclusions and make recommendations.

The fourth type of activity, called "transfer of innovative experience", also includes four classes of activities, each class having specific tasks. If the first class, ie "goal setting" implies the separation of the main tasks of the transmission of new pedagogical ideas, the second class - "task planning" is to determine the composition and sequence of actions for the transmission of news, the development of calendar plans.

The third grade, called the "transfer process," requires the implementation of an effective didactic process, that is, the organization of goal-oriented learning activities for students. The final fourth step - analysis and evaluation - monitors and evaluates the signal movement.

The analysis of the content of the future teacher-innovator work showed that, as expected, the transfer and transfer of innovative experience, that is, the educational process and a lot of time is spent on its preparation. (Types I and IV - 68.3%). However, the development of pedagogical innovations takes almost a third of the teacher's working time (type II - 30.9%).

A lot of time is spent on technical and methodological support and analysis of its results in conducting pedagogical testing (6.2%). That is a fact, of course. True, time can be significantly reduced (even if necessary) by pre-preparing the test class and reworking the research steps.

1. The research process can be expressed in two stages:

Break down a non-standardized list of knowledge;

Systematize selected knowledge, check them for completeness and representativeness.

The empirical material obtained using the methods developed and tested during the research was the basis for fragmenting the knowledge. As a result, we have identified the

knowledge used by the teacher in the implementation of innovative activities in general secondary schools. This knowledge was analyzed for completeness.

Systematization of the selected knowledge was carried out using generalization levels. The first and second of these levels are simplified for the selection of knowledge required by different subject teachers, while the third and fourth levels of generalization of knowledge in the field of innovation vary depending on the direction of teacher training.

At the first level of generalization of knowledge, a set of theories combined with a common feature, which gives a holistic idea of the laws and important connections in different areas of reality, was chosen. Thus, the sum of the total knowledge extracted at this level is expressed as follows:

a) the field of methodological knowledge, which includes theories that reveal the laws of innovation, methods of pedagogical research;

b) the field of psychological and pedagogical knowledge includes theories that reveal and explain the laws of innovative processes.

c) the field of methodological knowledge combines a set of theories that reveal the sequence of the introduction of pedagogical innovations in the teaching process and evaluate their effectiveness.

g) the field of special knowledge consists of a set of theories explaining the features of pedagogical innovation for a particular subject.

At the second level of generalization, theories were divided according to how reality revealed laws in a particular area. Consequently, the second level of knowledge is expressed by a clear (concrete) scope of knowledge in the areas previously identified.

Field of methodological knowledge:

- The scope of knowledge on theoretical methodology: methodology as a system of innovative knowledge and a system of innovative activities; methodological support of research activities in the field of pedagogical innovation; methodological analysis of the object and subject of innovative research.

- The scope of knowledge on the normative methodology: pedagogical innovation is a scientific justification of its difference from other forms, which is aimed at changing the objective reality; determination of the attitude of innovative work in the field of pedagogy to science (characteristics of the purpose, separation of special objects, application of special methods and means of understanding, uniformity of terminology); grouping innovative research; logic of pedagogical research.

The field of psychological and pedagogical knowledge - the scope of psychological knowledge combines a set of theories that reveal the laws of psychological processes of innovative activity, mental states and characteristics of the individual;

- The range of pedagogical knowledge represents a set of theories that explain the laws of innovative processes of teaching and educating the younger generation.

Field of methodical knowledge:

- scope of knowledge on the study and generalization of innovative experience;

- The scope of knowledge on the transfer of pedagogical innovations to new situations;

- The scope of knowledge on the introduction of innovation using effective teaching methods and tools.

Field of special knowledge:

- The scope of knowledge on the development of pedagogical innovations in order to improve the content of a particular subject;
- The scope of knowledge on the application of innovative ideas for specific disciplines;
- The scope of knowledge to determine the effectiveness of innovative processes for the study of a particular science.

Subsequent detailing of knowledge is related to the identification of the highlighted objects in each subject area using key concepts that describe the most important aspects of the innovation object.

Thus, the set of theoretical knowledge required for a future teacher to carry out innovative activities is a standard list, which is reflected in the three levels of generalization and represents the ultimate goal of developing a "knowledge" indicator.

The next stage in the development of the "Knowledge" indicator is to obtain predictive information to compile the final version of the standard list of knowledge. An expert evaluation method was used during the study to obtain predictive information.

Experts were asked to assess the extent to which the scope of knowledge required for teachers to implement innovative activities in school is fully expressed in the standard list (in points), as well as their importance for two time intervals:

- for today;
- for the future.

Assessment of each scope of knowledge by experts and analysis of this assessment allows to determine the correct distribution of workload, the allocation of time for the study of a particular subject in the development of curricula, as well as the direction and level of innovative training of future teachers. The results of the expert evaluation analysis are presented in the form of a diagram (Figure 1.3).

The Sum of expert evaluation positions

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